

Geo-political Analysis of Unfencing International Border through MADM Strategy: A Case Study of N.C. Nagar area, Tripura

Pratibha Karki, Research Scholar, Department of Statistics, Tripura University
Stabak Roy, Fahrenheit Fellow, University of Gdansk, Poland
Saptarshi Mitra, Associate Professor, Department of Geography & Disaster Management,
Tripura University
Nalanda Roy, Professor, Department of Political Science and International Studies,
Georgia Southern University
Samrat Hore*, Assistant Professor, Department of Statistics, Tripura University
*Corresponding author: Samrat Hore

Abstract

This study evaluates the geopolitical implications of international border fences between India and Bangladesh, focusing specifically on the N.C. Nagar area in Tripura. As of December 23, 2015, the Indian government had authorized the construction of 3,326.14 kilometers of barbed wire fencing along the border, with 2,708.77 kilometers completed. N.C. Nagar is one of the unfenced regions, which raises critical questions about the effectiveness of border fences in controlling illegal cross-border activities and their influence on bilateral relations. Through an in-depth examination of N.C. Nagar, this research elucidates the intricate dynamics and repercussions of unfenced borders. Apart from the widely used graphical analysis and testing approaches to measure the associations between the factors through contingency tables, a fuzzy-based decision-making approach named the multi-attribute decision-making (MADM) strategy has been considered here. A weighted decision matrix has been proposed to solve the MADM strategy through an efficient iterative search algorithm called the Variable Constrained Neighborhood Search Algorithm (VCNS) which identifies and prioritizes significant factors affecting the daily lives of residents. This research enriches the existing literature on border security and highlights the potential advantages and challenges of considering unfenced international borders in the India-Bangladesh context.

Keywords: International Border Issues, Unfenced Border, Variable Neighborhood Search, Decision Matrix, Fuzzy Set Theory.

Introduction

Bangladesh, strategically located at the crossroads of South Asia, has experienced notable economic growth in recent years, emerging as one of the fastest-growing economies in the region. However, persistent political instability poses significant threats not only to its governance but also to the broader regional stability of South Asia. The political landscape of Bangladesh has been characterized by a history of conflict, marked by electoral violence, corruption, and governance challenges (Datta,2005; Rahman and Rashid,2018). This instability is further compounded by socio-economic disparities that have left large segments of the population disenfranchised (Asadullah and Chakravorty, 2019; Mahmud et al., 2008). The complexities of Bangladeshi politics have implications that extend beyond its borders, as internal

unrest can foster radicalization and exacerbate tensions in neighboring countries (Rahman and Rashid,2018). Understanding these dynamics is crucial for comprehending the security landscape of the region, especially given the interconnectedness of South Asian countries (Islam,2020, Tahir et al.,2019). Since gaining independence in 1971, Bangladesh has faced a tumultuous political environment. The nation has oscillated between military rule and civilian governance, marked by political violence, assassinations, and deep-rooted tensions between major political parties, primarily the Awami League and the Bangladesh Nationalist Party (BNP). These factions frequently resort to violence to resolve disputes, leading to a highly polarized society. The International Crisis Group (2020) highlights a growing authoritarian trend within the political climate, where dissent is often suppressed, and civil liberties curtailed. This environment fosters discontent and creates fertile ground for radicalization among marginalized groups, potentially leading to the emergence of extremist factions that threaten regional stability (Tahir et al.2019).

The political instability in Bangladesh is further exacerbated by significant socio-economic disparities. Although the country has made remarkable strides in economic development, with an average GDP growth rate exceeding 6% in recent years (World Bank, 2021), the benefits of this growth have not been evenly distributed. Rural areas continue to lag behind urban centers, resulting in widespread disenfranchisement and frustration among the population (Ahmed, 2020; Hossain, 2019). The lack of inclusive governance exacerbates these inequalities, limiting the ability of marginalized communities to express their grievances. Such disenfranchisement can lead to heightened tensions, pushing disaffected groups towards violence as a means of political expression (Cattaneo et al., 2022). The geopolitical landscape of South Asia adds another layer of complexity to the situation. Bangladesh's strategic position between India and Myanmar places it at the center of regional power dynamics. China's increasing influence in Bangladesh, primarily through investments and infrastructure projects under the Belt and Road Initiative, aims to counterbalance Indian dominance in the region (Chakma, 2019; Aditya, 2021). However, this relationship poses risks; internal political instability could render Bangladesh a pawn in larger geopolitical conflicts (Aditya, 2021). Analysts have noted that external interventions in domestic politics often exacerbate existing tensions, complicating efforts to achieve sustainable peace (Cheng et al.,2018). The instability in Bangladesh has significant implications for its neighbors, particularly India. A politically unstable Bangladesh could lead to an influx of refugees seeking safety across the border, as historically observed during periods of crisis (Chowdhary, 2020). This refugee flow can strain resources and exacerbate existing socio-political challenges within India, especially in states like West Bengal and Assam, which are already dealing with complex migration and identity issues (Pattanaik, 2021). Moreover, the rise of extremist ideologies in Bangladesh can spill over into neighboring countries, heightening the

risk of cross-border militancy and further destabilizing the region (Malji et al.,2022). So, the political imbalance in Bangladesh poses a significant threat to the stability of South Asia. The potential for internal unrest, coupled with socio-economic disparities and geopolitical tensions, creates a precarious situation that demands urgent attention. By addressing the root causes of political instability and fostering a more inclusive society, Bangladesh can work toward a more stable future one that contributes positively to the security and prosperity of the entire South Asian region.

The India-Bangladesh Border: Complexities and Challenges

The border between India and Bangladesh, like all other boundaries on the Indian sub-continent, was placed artificially over the preexisting physical as well as cultural landscape by British colonial rulers. Bangladesh and India have a 4,096 km long border, making up roughly 27 % of India's whole land border, making it the longest of all the neighboring countries. Five states sharing the international border in between India and Bangladesh are Assam, Meghalaya, West Bengal, Tripura and Mizoram. Several variables hamper the efficient management of this lengthy border. These include difficult terrain, unresolved boundary disputes, unauthorized Bangladeshi immigration into India, the existence of Indian rebel bases in Bangladesh, and the activity of transnational criminal gangs and networks. Up to the border, numerous densely populated areas are located characterized by fertile, flat ground near the border. The zero line is surrounded by more than a hundred villages. The ethnic characteristics of the population are similar on both sides of the border, making it challenging to distinguish between Indian and Bangladeshi countrymen. Traditional cross-border links between different ethnic groups and cultures are still present today.

India–Bangladesh border issues have been the most sensitive and challenging for both countries. In a study, Das (2008) examined the issues that have arisen along this border, as well as the suggestions made in a report by the Group of Ministers(May 23, 2001) on Border Management and the steps the Government has taken to address the issues. The article made additional recommendations and urged the Indian Government to improve border management in a practical and people-sensitive manner. The Group of Ministers (GoM) said in its assessment that certain inherent issues prevent the nation's boundaries from being successfully administered. To start, most borders are either disputed or not precisely defined. Many are artificial barriers that do not follow a natural barrier, making them very permeable. Since Partition in 1947, enclaves along the India-Bangladesh border have posed both conceptual as well as pragmatic challenges for both countries. National security, belonging, and control are starkly contrasted in these pockets of India inside Bangladesh and vice versa. Jason Cons (2013) investigates the

politics of creating communities along the Bangladesh-India border by looking at the public and private histories and sense of identity in a Bangladeshi enclave, a sovereign region of Bangladesh entirely surrounded by Indian territory. Jason Cons (2016) contends that these spaces are crucial for reconsidering the formation of territory in South Asia now through ethnographic and historical analysis. His Book “Sensitive Space” looks at how these sites represent a variety of concerns about territory, land, and national existence and prompts us to think about why some places end up emerging as controversial and frequently violent spaces at the edges of nation and state.

A number of aspects of managing the Indo-Bangladesh border are examined by Jamwal (2004), including difficulties in managing it and Bangladesh’s internal political and security environment and recommendations for ways to enhance border management. The study regarding the Indo-Bangladesh border fence was also studied by McDuie-Ra (2014) where he investigates the various fence-related narratives at the national level in India and in the border region itself, with a particular emphasis on the state of Meghalaya. These stories demonstrate the political stances that are taken on the border fence in these various settings, as well as the ways in which it is debated and interpreted. Another study, Shewly (2013), deals with how enclave dwellers experience vulnerability when their lives are caught between two states, drawing on an ethnography of the enclaves in India and Bangladesh. Geographically, these enclaves are in one nation, yet they are politically and legally belonging to another. The study makes the argument that social and gendered components are crucial for a nuanced approach to this concept, in addition to the sovereign creation of bare life.

The present paper provides a detailed analysis of the N.C. Nagar area which illuminates the intricate dynamics and implications of unfenced international borders. This study also aims to identify and address various challenges faced by residents in the area of study encounter. To achieve this objective, multiple responses have been collected from residents of the unfenced region, Nabadwipchandra Nagar along the India-Bangladesh border. The analysis is structured in two stages: the first stage tests the concept of marginal independence in favor of marginal association, while the second stage proposes a Variable Constraint Neighborhood Search Algorithm (VCNS) for multi-attribute decision-making (MADM) within a possibility environment. This algorithm represents a significant advancement over traditional methods, as it offers enhanced computational efficiency and adaptability in handling the complexities and variability inherent in decision-making processes. Unlike conventional approaches that can be resource-intensive and less effective in dynamic contexts, the VCNS algorithm provides a tractable and flexible framework capable of addressing diverse criteria.

By employing this innovative methodological approach, the study not only deepens the understanding of local complexities but also aids in developing actionable strategies that improve border management and community welfare in unfenced areas.

Research Domain

The Nabadwipchandra Nagar (N.C.) area, situated in the northeastern state of Tripura in India, shares a border with Bangladesh. Like many other border regions, it has historically witnessed tensions, conflicts, and challenges related to border security and cross-border movements. However, in recent years, there has been growing debate and discussion surrounding the idea of unfencing international borders to foster better regional cooperation, economic integration, and diplomatic relations. The N.C. Nagar area, situated along the India-Bangladesh border, is influenced by various geo-political factors that shape its dynamics and present both challenges and opportunities. These factors include Security Concerns, Cross-Border Trade and Economic Impact, Diplomatic Relations. The border fence was primarily erected to enhance security measures and prevent illegal activities such as smuggling, human trafficking, and the infiltration of extremist elements.

The study has been considered an unfencing area of the state Tripura to identify several problems that are faced by the inhabitants of the study area, Nabadwipchandra nagar. This gram panchayet area is under Sonamura Nagar Panchayat (3.47°N, 91.27°E). According to Census 2011, Sonamura had a population of 10,074. Males constituted 51 % of the population and females 49 %. The objective of the present study is to systematically identify the challenges encountered by the inhabitants of N.C. Nagar. Data was collected from 147 respondents selected through simple random sampling, utilizing structured interviews to facilitate comprehensive investigation. The responses were evenly distributed between male and female participants. The collected data was subsequently analyzed using descriptive and explanatory methods, providing insights into the socio-economic issues facing this border community. (Fig.1)

Fig. 1: Location Map of the Study Area (Source: Prepared by the authors, 2024)

The presence of the fence has helped control the movement of unauthorized individuals and goods to a certain extent, contributing to improved border security. The border fence has had implications for cross-border trade and economic relations in the N.C. Nagar area. While the fence restricts informal trade and smuggling, it also limits the scope for legal trade and economic cooperation between India and Bangladesh. The removal of the fence could potentially facilitate greater cross-border economic integration, enabling the region to tap into the benefits of enhanced trade and investment opportunities. The presence of the border fence has influenced diplomatic relations between India and Bangladesh. While it has addressed certain security concerns, it has also been a source of tension and occasional disputes. The decision to unfence the border would require diplomatic negotiations and mutual agreement between the two countries, necessitating careful consideration of various political and strategic factors.

Graphical Representation of Data

Data visualization is the graphical representation of information and data. To have a vivid picture of the various information we collected related to this study, we present them graphically as follows:

Fig. 2: Number of respondents along with their respective houses

Representation of the number of members in their respective houses and the majority of them belongs to the age group of 35 – 39, 45 – 49, and 60 -above is shown in Fig.2. It can be observed that 58.50% of respondents, i.e. almost 6 out of 10 people, have 4 to 5 members in their houses and the remaining 41.5% are scattered among other groups.

Fig. 3: Monthly income of the respondents

Money plays a significant role in our lives. It allows us to meet our basic requirements, such as food, shelter, and healthcare. Figure 3 represents the monthly income of the respondents of the study area. Among all the respondents, 80.95% belongs to the income group 5000-10000, 10000-15000, and 15000-2000. Observing the above diagram, it can be concluded that most of them belongs to lower-income groups.

Fig. 4: Members(4A) and educational qualification(4B) of respondents

Education raises the quality of life and creates opportunities for acquiring knowledge and developing skills. Education has a multi-faceted impact on society, it can be observed that most of the people (77%) have completed their education up to the secondary level and very few people are graduates (1%).

Fig. 5: Distance of nearest primary(5A) and secondary(5B) schools

Distance plays a very important role in the decision to select schools. Figure 5 depicts the distance from their house to the primary and secondary school. Since more than $(\frac{3}{4})^{th}$ of the population resides within a range of 0 to 0.5 km, we can assume that primary schools are within walking distance of their homes. However, secondary schools are a little bit farther away than primary schools.

Fig. 6: The need for presentation of identity card while going to school

The requirement to present an identity card in order to enter a school is depicted in figure 6. More than 60% of individuals are required to present identity cards when entering schools, while 40% of people have alternative options, like presenting daily passes.

Fig. 7: Distance of the nearest primary health center

Primary health centers (PHC)s play a crucial role in providing basic healthcare services to individuals residing in a specific area. They provide integrated curative and preventive healthcare to the rural population and serve as the initial point of contact between the community and the medical officer. According to the data, the majority (58%) of the people reside within the range of 1 km diameter of PHC (Fig.7).

Fig. 8: Distance of the nearest market from the house (8A) and vendors facing problems in selling vegetables (8B)

Food is essential for survival, so it must be inaccessible distance. The majority of the people (94%) live at a distance of 1 – 1.5 km radius area (fig. 8). Individuals encounter difficulties selling their vegetables due to certain regional regulations.

Methodology

The study aims to identify and address the issues that are faced by the respondents of the study area. To achieve this, the study has employed two methods i.e. Multiple Marginal Independence (MMI) test and Variable Constrained Neighborhood Search (VCNS) Algorithm. MMI test examines if there is a significant relationship between two attributes/responses. Additionally, a weighted decision matrix have been introduced to solve the MADM strategy through an efficient iterative search algorithm called the constrained variable neighborhood search algorithm. The VCNS optimization algorithm helps to identify the significant factors based on their assumed weights and then rank the factors regarding their importance in solving the issues for the betterment of the daily life of those inhabitants.

- **Multiple Marginal Independence (MMI) test**

Let's consider two questions with multiple responses A_i and A_j with q_{ij} as the affirmative answers to A_i and A_j . A table that summarises these responses is called a marginal table, where each q_{ij} is a sum of affirmative responses to items A_i and A_j . The marginal probability of a positive response to A_i and A_j is denoted by π_{ij} and its maximum likelihood estimate is $\hat{\pi}_{ij} = \frac{q_{ij}}{n}$. The hypotheses for the test of multiple marginal independence (MMI) test are

$$H_0 : \pi_{ij} = \pi_i \pi_j \text{ for } i=1 \dots r \text{ and } j=1 \dots c$$

H_1 : At least one equality does not hold

where, $\pi_{ij} = P(A_i = 1, A_j = 1)$, $\pi_{i.} = P(A_i = 1)$ and $\pi_{.j} = P(A_j = 1)$. According to Agresti and Liu (1999), respective test statistic for MMI can be expressed as

$$\chi_{MMI}^2 = n \sum_{i=1}^r \sum_{j=1}^c \frac{(\hat{\pi}_{ij} - \hat{\pi}_{i.} \hat{\pi}_{.j})^2}{\hat{\pi}_{i.} \hat{\pi}_{.j} (1 - \hat{\pi}_{i.}) (1 - \hat{\pi}_{.j})} \quad (3.1)$$

While proceeding towards Variable Constrained Neighborhood Search Algorithm(VCNS) the following terminology and notations are used that are connected to the key findings of the study.

- **Formulation of multi-attribute decision matrix**

Let us assume that, $M = \{M_1, M_2, M_3, \dots, M_u\}$ represents the family of u distinct potential solutions and N be the family of v distinct characteristics, where $N = \{N_1, N_2, N_3, \dots, N_v\}$. Decision matrix (D^{MADM}) of order $u \times v$ for each of the u distinct potentials against each of the v different characteristics is formulated as: $D^{MADM} = ((x_{ij}, \mu_{ij}(F_j)))$, for $i=1(1)u, j=1(1)v$.

- **Normalized Decision Matrix**

The normalization approaches used by multi-attribute decision-making (MADM) methodologies enable the grouping of characteristics with numerical and comparable data. Depending on the subject domain, data normalization has a variety of definitions. To strengthen the coherence and effectiveness of managing data, data normalization has been considered as a process where data attributes inside a data model are organised in tables (Vafaci et al.,2016). The Simple Additive Weighting (SAW) method, often referred to as the weighted sum method, is likely the most well-known and popular MADM method (Hwang et al.1981). The fundamental idea of SAW is to obtain a weighted sum of each alternative's performance ratings across all attributes (Fishburn,1967; MacCrimmon,1968). In order to provide a comparable scale for all ratings, the SAW approach typically calls for normalizing the decision matrix in X by :

$$\begin{aligned} n_{ij} &= \frac{x_{ij}}{x_{max}}, \text{ if } j \text{ is the benefit-attribute} \\ &= 1 - \frac{x_{ij}}{x_{max}}, \text{ if } j \text{ is the cost-attribute} \end{aligned} \quad \dots(4.4)$$

where n_{ij} ($0 \leq n_{ij} \leq 1$) is defined as the normalized performance rating of alternatives N_j on M_i . To ensure that the ratings' relative order of magnitude is maintained, this normalization method changes all of the ratings in a linear (proportional) manner (Nijkamp and van,1977) . In this work, we have considered the formula for the benefit-attribute to normalize the decision matrix.

- **Weight on possible solution: An approach of Robustness over Decision Matrix**

Generally, a decision matrix has been formulated to select the favorable potential solution (alternative) among all possible potential solutions (alternatives). It has been assumed that those potential solutions or the alternatives are equally weighted for the sake of mathematical convenience. But in real-life situations, such weights may not be equal. For example, a policy maker may give more weight-age value to the specific solution (s) or alternative (s) among all possible solutions or alternatives due to the convenience of the policy implementation. In this study, we have addressed such a situation and considered a weighting vector on possible potential solutions or alternatives. Such weight vector has played a crucial role in making robust decisions on the selection of favorable potential solutions or alternatives by addressing both policy maker preference and respondents preference. In this study, the weight vector W representing the relative significance of all possible u potential solutions (alternatives) is defined as, $W = (W_1, W_2, \dots, W_u)$, where $\sum_{l=1}^u W_l = 1$.

- **Variable Constraint Neighborhood Search (VCNS) Algorithm**

Considering the various weights of potential solutions (alternative), a variable constraint neighborhood search (VCNS) algorithm has been proposed to obtain the best alternative for MADM strategy under a possible environment. Selecting a good initial solution ensures quick convergence to attain the best alternative. A good initial has been obtained by the widely applied re-randomization method. After obtaining a good initial, the first step of neighborhood search is adopted to attain a better initial solution (alternative), and later, through the second step of neighborhood search, the best final solution (best alternative) is achieved.

- **Initial Allocation in Experimental Units**

Selecting a good initial is always preferable; otherwise, a worse initial may lead to a bad final solution. To avoid such worst possible situation, a repeated randomization method or re-randomization method by Xu and Kalbfleish (2013) has been carried out, where among the t times randomization method, the best possible solution will be selected as a good initial solution as refereed in Hore et al. (2014, 2016). Here, we have considered $t = 10$.

• Neighborhood Search Algorithm

After selecting a good initial solution through the re-randomization method, a search algorithm consisting of constrained weights has been carried out to attain the best final potential solution or best alternative among all possible alternatives. Let us consider the objective function (possibility coefficient of variation) $V(\gamma)$, to be minimized for a potential solution vector γ , consisting of m potential solutions among all possible M possible potential solutions. Remaining $(M-m)$ potential solutions are framed into another vector δ , where $\delta = (\delta_1, \delta_2, \dots, \delta_{(M-m)})$. The proposed algorithm may be described as follows:

Step 1 (Good initial selection): Start with an initial potential solution vector, denoted by $\gamma^{(0)}$ and the corresponding objective function $V(\gamma^{(0)})$.

Step 2 (Subject to the Constraint): The design is fitted to a new weighted setup subject to the condition $W_i \leq \max(W_{(i)} \gamma^{(0)})$, when the corresponding objective function $V(\gamma^{(0)})$ is minimum.

Step 3 (First Step Neighborhood search): Let us consider the first step neighborhood $N_1(\gamma^{(0)})$ of the initial potential solution vector $\gamma^{(0)}$ as $N_1(\gamma^{(0)}) = (\gamma_i^{(0)}, \delta_j)$ where $\gamma_i^{(0)'}$ is the sample size of $(m-1)$, which is constructed as $\gamma_i^{(0)'} = \gamma^{(0)'} - \gamma_i'$ for $i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, m$ and $j = 1, 2, 3, \dots, (M-m)$; $\delta_j' \in \delta'$.

Step 4: (Selection of better initial): Compute $V(\gamma')$, for all $\gamma' \in N_1(\gamma^{(0)})$, if $\min \{V(\gamma'), \gamma' \in N_1(\gamma^{(0)}) \leq V(\gamma^{(0)})\}$, then choose the next improved allocation to be $\gamma^{(0)'} = \arg \arg \{V(\gamma'), \gamma' \in N_1(\gamma^{(0)})\}$ otherwise, choose $\gamma^{(0)'}$ randomly from among the allocations in $\{\gamma^{(0)'}, N_{\gamma^{(0)'}}\}$ with probabilities given by

$$P_{\gamma^{(0)'}} = \frac{V_{\gamma^{(0)'}}}{D_{\gamma^{(0)'}}}, \text{ where, } D_{\gamma^{(0)'}} = V_{\gamma^{(0)'}} + \sum_{\gamma' \in N_1(\gamma^{(0)'})} \{V(\gamma')\}.$$

Step 5: (Selection of best initial): Replace $\gamma^{(0)}$ by $\gamma^{(0)'}$ and repeat step 3,4 until it convergences with some desired accuracy. A stochastic approach has been suggested while successive returns to the same potential solution vector $\gamma^{(0)'}$, attaining the level of accuracy by obtaining the respective probability value at least 0.90. Here at i^{th} successive return ($i \geq 1$) of the same potential solution vector $\gamma^{(0)'}$, the respective probability value is calculated as $p^{[i]}_{\gamma^{(0)'}} = p_{\gamma^{(0)'}} \times i$, where $p_{\gamma^{(0)'}}$ is calculated as previous.

Step 6: The best m -dimensional initial solution vector is $\gamma^{(0)'}$ and the alternatives are ranked accordingly.

Step 7: Select the new $(M-m)$ -dimensional vector $\delta^{(0)'}$ of remaining $(M-m)$ objects.

Step 8: (Towards the second step, Neighborhood Search): Start with $l=1$. Select the respective best

solution vector as $\gamma^{(l-1)'}$ and the remaining object solution vector as $\delta^{(l-1)'}$.

Step 9: Let the second step neighborhood be constructed as $N_2(\gamma^{(l)}) = (\gamma^{(l-1)'}, \delta_k)$, where $\delta_k \in \delta^{(l-1)'}$, $k=1,2,3,\dots,m_{\delta^{(l-1)'}}$ and $m_{\delta^{(l-1)'}}$ is the number of objects in corresponding remaining object solution vector $\delta^{(l-1)'}$.

Step10: Compute $V(\gamma')$, for all $\gamma' \in N_2(\gamma^{(l)'})$, select $\gamma^{(l)'}$ as new best solution vector where $\gamma^{(l)' = \arg \min\{V(\gamma'), \gamma' \in N_2(\gamma^{(l)'})\}$.

Step11: Rank the alternatives of the new best solution vector $\gamma^{(l)'}$, and also calculate the new remaining object-wise solution $\delta^{(l)'}$.

Step12: (**Moving towards optimality**) : Replacing l by $l+1$ and start the algorithm repeat from step 8.

Step13: (**Stopping Condition**): Till $l = (M-m)-1$ the algorithm continues and ranks the alternatives.

Step 14: (**End of Search**): The process terminates with only one remaining alternative in the remaining object solution vector, which will be taken into consideration as the highest (lowest) ranking value, as the objective function is to be minimized (maximized).

Figure 9: Flow Chart of the proposed VCNS algorithm

Result and Discussions

To fulfill the objective of the study two multiple-response questions Q_1 and Q_2 has been selected from the survey questionnaire where the total number of individuals responded to the questions. The first question assesses the problems faced by the respondents and the second question deals with how the permanent problems can be solved. The re-responses to the above-mentioned question Q_1 are considered as:- A_1 : Id card showing related problems on the daily basis, A_2 : Need of daily basis permission for going to daily work, A_3 : Permission to be asked while having Guest, A_4 : Permission regarding organising any function such as marriage ceremony, death ceremony etc., A_5 :Permission regarding selling and buying rice from rice mill, A_6 : Permission regarding buying and selling of vehicles related problems.

The responses of Q_2 are considered as:- C_1 : Stop daily Id verification at STOP/checkpoint for the locals, C_2 : Stop checking of the Guest ID proof at STOP/checkpoint, C_3 : Stop daily basis checking for local inhabitants, C_4 : Stop verification while buying and selling of vegetables/rice, C_5 : Stop the procedure for asking the Permission of organising functions (such as: marriage ceremonies, death ceremonies etc.), C_6 :Stop asking Permission in a case of medical urgency.

The multi-responses of 147 respondents for the above questions are collected and the data has been aggregated in Table 1. The data represents the number of cases with aYes response for the corresponding row/column.

Table 1: Contingency table with multiple response data

What are the problems faced by the respondents?	How can permanent problems be solved?						Total(π_i)
	i	ii	iii	iv	v	vi	
1	96	91	72	11	45	21	108
2	90	86	31	8	45	22	101
3	94	90	74	10	41	17	104
4	44	21	14	2	27	14	49
5	12	11	7	7	12	13	30
6	14	14	11	3	10	11	32
Total(π_j)	124	97	76	12	46	47	147

To compute test statistic (3.1), one can create 36 (2×2) tables and sum up the traditional Pearson Chi-square tests. The chi-square statistic is the sum of 36 individual components. Using SPSS, we calculated the chi-square test (3.1). Under the simple random sampling assumption on which the above test is based, the observed result for the statistic χ_{MMI}^2 leads to a strong

rejection of the null hypothesis of marginal independence between issues faced and permanent problems to be solved. The result is shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Chi-Square tests

Problems faced	Permanent problems
Pearson Chi-square	78.121
degrees of freedom	25
Significant	.000*

It has been observed (Table 2) that the calculated value of chi-square is 78.121 with degrees of freedom 25 having P-value is < 0.05 . So, there is a strong rejection of the null hypothesis of marginal independence between Q1 and Q2.

To explore the application of the proposed algorithm same questions with same alternatives has been considered. The decision matrix corresponding to the value of different alternatives according to their attributes is presented in the following table (Table 3).

For the sake of mathematical demonstration, we have considered here the weight vector W is as $(W_{C_1}, W_{C_2}, W_{C_3}, W_{C_4}, W_{C_5}, W_{C_6}) = (0.1, 0.1, 0.1, 0.1, 0.1, 0.5)$. As per policy maker, more preference has been given to the relaxation on emergency medical cases.

Table 3: Decision matrix corresponds to the value of different alternatives according to their attributes

	A_1	A_2	A_3	A_4	A_5	A_6
C_1	96	90	94	44	12	14
C_2	91	86	90	21	11	14
C_3	72	31	74	14	7	11
C_4	11	8	10	2	7	3
C_5	45	45	41	27	12	10
C_6	21	22	17	14	13	11

As the initial step, the decision matrix of Table 3 is first normalized using equation (4.1) for beneficial attribute criteria and reported in Table 4.

Table 4: Normalized Decision matrix

	A_1	A_2	A_3	A_4	A_5	A_6
C_1	1	1	1	1	0.9231	1
C_2	0.9479	0.9555	0.9574	0.4772	0.8461	1
C_3	0.75	0.3444	0.7872	0.3182	0.5385	0.7857
C_4	0.1146	0.0888	0.1064	0.0455	0.5385	0.2143
C_5	0.4688	0.5	0.4362	0.6136	0.9231	0.7143
C_6	0.2188	0.2444	0.1809	0.3182	1	0.7857

The possible mean for each of the alternatives is evaluated as follows:

$$\bar{X}^F = \{(C_1, 0.987179), (C_2, 0.864058), (C_3, 0.587339), (C_4, 0.184676), (C_5, 0.60932),$$

$(C_6, 0.45799)\}$. Here, we have used the re-randomization method to arrive at a good initial solution, which involves selecting a sample of three out of the six alternatives at random and repeating the process 10 times. All the 10 random samples and their respective values of possibility coefficient of variation(objective function) are reported in Table 5.

Table 5: Selection of good initial solution through re-randomization

Sample No	Random Sample	Value of objective function(P_{CV})
1	(C_1, C_6, C_2)	35.9749
2	(C_4, C_2, C_5)	62.0993
3	(C_6, C_5, C_3)	14.8249
4	(C_2, C_5, C_6)	31.8763
5	(C_4, C_1, C_5)	67.6203
6	(C_1, C_5, C_4)	67.6203
7	(C_2, C_3, C_5)	22.3919
8	(C_4, C_5, C_6)	51.5713
9	(C_4, C_5, C_1)	67.6203
10	(C_2, C_4, C_6)	68.0640

With the smallest value of the possible co-efficient of variation, 14.8249, we have identified a good initial solution as (C_6, C_5, C_3) , denoted as $\gamma^{(0)}$. Now we construct the first stage neighborhood of $\gamma^{(0)}$

with $\delta=(C_1, C_2, C_4)$, a set of remaining objects following subject to the constraint $W_{C_i} \leq \max(W_{C_6}, W_{C_5}, W_{C_3})$. The construction of the first-stage neighborhood of $\gamma^{(0)'}$ is reported in the following table, Table 6.

Table 6: Construction of first-step neighborhood of $\gamma^{(0)}=(C_6, C_5, C_3)$

Sample No	Random Sample	Value of objective function(P_{CV})
1	(C_1, C_5, C_3)	30.8774
2	(C_6, C_1, C_3)	40.7195
3	(C_6, C_5, C_1)	39.7990
4	(C_6, C_5, C_2)	31.8763
5	(C_6, C_2, C_3)	32.5931
6	(C_2, C_5, C_3)	22.3919
7	(C_6, C_5, C_4)	51.5714
8	(C_6, C_4, C_3)	50.1403
9	(C_4, C_5, C_3)	51.9227

After the first iteration, by constructing the first-step neighborhood of the good initial solution $\gamma^{(0)}=(C_6, C_5, C_3)$, we have observed that there is no better initial solution than the previously mentioned one. So we consider (C_6, C_5, C_3) as the best initial solution with the minimum value of 14.8249. Now we can repeat steps 3 to 5 of the proposed algorithm and found (C_6, C_5, C_3) is the final best initial solution, denoted by $\gamma^{(0)'}$ after several iterations

with the respective probability of more than 0.90. According to step 6 of the algorithm, we have ranked the alternatives and found $C_6 < C_5 < C_3$. For better approximations, relative weighted ranking has been done and found $W_3C_3 < W_5C_5 < W_6C_6$. Following steps 8 onward of the variable constraint neighborhood search (VCNS) algorithm, we have found the respective best alternative neighbor in each level of the second-stage neighborhood and reported in Table 7.

Table 7: Construction of second-step neighborhood of $\gamma^{(0)' }=(C_3, C_5, C_6)$

Level	Best Solution	Ranking
1	(C_3, C_5, C_6, C_2)	$C_3 < C_5 < C_6 < C_2$
2	$(C_3, C_5, C_6, C_2, C_1)$	$C_3 < C_5 < C_6 < C_2 < C_1$

Succeeding up to Step 14 of the proposed variable constraint neighborhood search algorithm, we have found the best solutions with the ranking of alternatives as $C_3 < C_5 < C_6 < C_2 < C_1$ and the remaining single alternative is C_4 . Hence, the final best solution of all alternatives is structured according to the ranking as $C_3 < C_5 < C_6 < C_2 < C_1 < C_4$. The ranking alternatives

express that C_3 is the ideal one, i.e., to stop checking daily for the people who regularly travel on a daily basis or work or make an alternative way. However, the alternative C_4 is the least preferable one.

Concluding Remarks

Without secure borders with its neighbors, any country would find it difficult to fulfill its proper role in world affairs at this moment of fundamental change. Since borders are shared with neighbors and its inhabitants, the policy maker must consider both the people and the state of the respective country when discussing borders and their management. Long and densely populated, the Indo-Bangladesh border is home to people who share a common history of development, culture, language, and rich heritage. The challenge of border management along this border is not just to secure the border but to do so without harming the economic and cultural interests of the people, who have long depended on one another through trade, commerce and cultural interdependence. The border regions were neglected for a very long time on the political and economic fronts because they are in the most remote part of the country and as a result it remained underdeveloped. The negligence of mainland forces resulted in cross-border movements, which compelled residents of the border region to rely on old systems and engage in them to survive. It is necessary to strengthen the infrastructure and economy of the border regions in order to interconnect them with the mainland. Equally crucial are ensuring the political happiness of the border people, providing proper security, bridging the cultural and communication divide between the border people and the national majority and cultivating cordial ties with their border people. Although much has been accomplished, much more work has to be done.

This present study considers an unfencing area between the India and Bangladesh border known as Nabadwipchandra Nagar in the state of Tripura. The goal of this study is to comprehend the socio-economic and political context of the study area and to, ascertain the issues that the respondents are facing and find their perspectives regarding the prioritisation of issues that the Government should address first. By the administration of a primary multiple-response survey of the inhabitants of the unfencing area, the research provides insight into the potential implications of unfencing borders with regard to security concerns, trade and economic exchanges, cultural interactions, and overall diplomatic relations. This study used primary data and multi-response analysis of the data to understand the current scenario. Since socio-economic factors—like income, education, and access to healthcare—have an impact on an individual's lifestyle, the study reveals that the majority of respondents (77%) have completed secondary school and can thus be classified as educated. When taking into account the income component,

it becomes clear that 80.95% of the population is in the income range of 5000 to 15000, which is higher than the below-the-poverty line (BPL). The presence of a medical facility in the residential area is another significant factor. Therefore, the primary health centers need to be the closest in the event of an emergency. It can be inferred that primary health care services are available in case of emergency since over half of the respondents live less than 0.5 km from the health center and 41% of the population lives between 0.5 and 1 km. The respondents of the study area desire the Government to take action towards the variety of issues that they regularly encounter. To understand the most prioritized issue that should be solved first by the Government according to the respondents, we use the VCNS algorithm taking into account some of these factors. According to the analysis, the respondents want to cease or find a different way to regularly check on local residents and those who travel frequently for work without endangering national security. The proposed algorithm makes it simple to identify the issue with the highest priority and draw inferences from it. The goal of the research is to help policy makers make decisions about which problems or issues should be resolved first by offering significant implications that will help them better understand the situation in border areas. However, every policy change will be evaluated in the context of unique perspectives that represent local social demands.

Acknowledgement

The first author gratefully acknowledges the financial support under the WISE Fellowship for Ph.D. (WISE-PhD) [File No.: DST/WISE-PhD/PM/2024/29 dated January 08, 2025] of the Ministry of Science and Technology, Govt. of India, for Research in Basic/Applied Sciences. The corresponding author is thankful to his former project student Miss Halima Begum for collecting primary data from the study area.

Declaration

The authors of the manuscript titled “Geo-political Analysis of Unfencing International Border through MADM Strategy: A Case Study of N.C. Nagar area, Tripura” hereby affirm that it is an original work authored by us. We confirm that **no part of the paper has been plagiarised (including self-plagiarism) and published previously in any format (print or electronic)**. Furthermore, we certify that all sources and references have been appropriately cited and acknowledged in accordance with the journal's guidelines.

Conflict of interest

The author(s) certify that there is no conflict of interest with any financial/research/academic organization for publication of the article.

References

1. Aditya, S. (2021). Bangladesh's dilemma between big brothers India and China: El dilema de Bangladesh entre los hermanos mayores India y China. *South Florida Journal of Development*, 2(3), 4468-4479.
2. Asadullah, M. N., & Chakravorty, N. T. (2019). Growth, governance and corruption in Bangladesh: a re-assessment. *Third World Quarterly*, 40(5), 947-965.
3. Cattaneo, A., Adukia, A., Brown, D. L., Christiaensen, L., Evans, D. K., Haakenstad, A., ... & Weiss, D. J. (2022). Economic and social development along the urban–rural continuum: New opportunities to inform policy. *World Development*, 157, 105941.
4. Chakma, B. (2019). The BRI and Sino-Indian geo-economic competition in Bangladesh: Coping strategy of a small state. *Strategic Analysis*, 43(3), 227-239.
5. Cheng, C., Goodhand, J., & Meehan, P. (2018). Synthesis paper: Securing and sustaining elite bargains that reduce violent conflict.
6. Chowdhary, N. (2020). Environmental refugees: a humanitarian crisis in India and Bangladesh. In *Refugee Crises and Third-World Economies: Policies and Perspectives* (pp. 37-43). Emerald Publishing Limited.
7. Cons, J. (2013). Narrating boundaries: Framing and contesting suffering, community, and belonging in enclaves along the India–Bangladesh border. *Political Geography*, 35, 37-46.
8. Cons, J. (2016). *Sensitive space: Fragmented territory at the India-Bangladesh border*. University of Washington Press.
9. Das, P. (2008). India–Bangladesh border management: A review of government's Response. *Strategic Analysis*, 32(3), 367-388.
10. Datta, S. (2005). Political violence in Bangladesh: trends and causes. *Strategic Analysis*, 29(3), 427-447.
11. Fishburn, P. C. (1967). Methods of estimating additive utilities. *Management science*, 13(7), 435-453.
12. Group of ministers' report on "reforming the national security system" on May 23, 2001. <https://archive.pib.gov.in/archive/releases98/lyr2001/rmay2001/23052001/r2305200110.html> (Accessed on Oct 23, 2024).

13. Hore, S., Dewanji, A., & Chatterjee, A. (2014). Design issues related to allocation of experimental units with known covariates into two treatment groups. *Journal of Statistical Planning and Inference*, 155, 117-126.
14. Hore, S., Dewanji, A., & Chatterjee, A. (2016). On optimal allocation of experimental units with known covariates into multiple treatment groups. *Calcutta Statistical Association Bulletin*, 68(1-2), 69-81.
15. Hwang, C. L., Yoon, K., Hwang, C. L., & Yoon, K. (1981). Methods for multiple attribute decision making. *Multiple attribute decision making: methods and applications a state-of-the-art survey*, 58-191.
16. Islam, M. T. (2020). Analysis the Main Characteristics and Dynamics of Sub-Regional Security Complex of South Asia. *IOSR Journal of Humanities and Social Sceince*, 25(5), 62.
17. Jamwal, N. S. (2004). Border management: Dilemma of guarding the India-Bangladesh border. *Strategic Analysis*, 28(1), 5-36.
18. MacCrimmon, K. R. (1968). Decision making among multiple-attribute alternatives: a survey and consolidated approach.
19. Mahmud, W., Ahmed, S., & Mahajan, S. (2008). Economic reforms, growth, and governance: The political economy aspects of Bangladesh's development surprise. *Leadership and growth*, 227.
20. Malji, A., Obana, L., & Hopkins, C. (2022). When Home Disappears: South Asia and the Growing Risk of Climate Conflict. *Terrorism and Political Violence*, 34(5), 939-957.
21. McDuire-Ra, D. (2014). The India–Bangladesh border fence: Narratives and political possibilities. *Journal of Borderlands Studies*, 29(1), 81-94.
22. Nijkamp, P., & van Delft, A. (1977). *Multi-criteria analysis and regional decision-making*. Springer Science & Business Media, 8.
23. Pattanaik, S. S. (2021). Refugees, Border and Identities: Rights and Habitat in East and Northeast India: Anindita Ghoshal, *New Delhi: Routledge, 2021, Hardback, ISBN: 9780367706951*, pp. 310.
24. Rahman, R., & Rashid, M. M. (2018). Political instability and economic growth in Bangladesh. *Peer-reviewed academic journal innovative issues and approaches in social sciences*.
25. Rahman, R., & Rashid, M. M. (2018). Political instability and economic growth in Bangladesh. *Peer-reviewed academic journal innovative issues and approaches in social sciences*.
26. Shewly, H. J. (2013). Abandoned spaces and bare life in the enclaves of the India–Bangladesh border. *Political Geography*, 32, 23-31.

27. Tahir, M., Kalhor, J. A., & Ahmad, A.(2019) The Emerging Intelligence Architecture of Internal Security & New Regional Dynamics in South Asia (2015-2018). *Global Social Sciences Review*.
28. Vafaei, N., Ribeiro, R. A., & Camarinha-Matos, L. M. (2016). Normalization techniques for multi-criteria decision making: analytical hierarchy process case study. In *Technological innovation for cyber-physical systems: 7th IFIP WG 5.5/SOCOLNET advanced doctoral conference on computing, electrical and industrial systems, DoCEIS 2016, Costa de Caparica, Portugal, April 11–13, 2016, Proceedings 7*, Springer International Publishing, 261-269
29. Xu, Z., & Kalbfleisch, J. D. (2013). Repeated randomization and matching in multi-arm trials. *Biometrics*, 69(4), 949-959.